

Is Quitt's climate classification still relevant? Challenges posed by recent climate change

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Abstract

Climate classifications based on fixed threshold values are increasingly challenged under recent climate change, yet remain broadly used. Accordingly, this contribution assesses the relevance of the widely used Quitt climate classification for the Czech Republic as a representative region of Central Europe. The original methodology, derived from the 1901–1950 period, was re-applied to a gridded dataset of multiple climate variables based on homogenised station series for the 1961–1990 and 1991–2020 periods to produce an updated version of the Quitt climate classification. For the 1991–2020 period, results indicate a significant expansion of the Warm group of climatic regions (by 30%) at the expense of the Moderately Warm and Cold groups. Following these spatial shifts, the Updated Quitt climate classification lost its explanatory power during this period. The original classification criterion (matching ≥ 12 of 14 variables) was met in only 5% of the Czech Republic due to a loss of internal consistency between temperature and precipitation characteristics: rising temperatures shifted climatic regions to higher elevations, while precipitation totals remained stable. The unsuitability of the original Quitt classification method emphasises the need for multivariate statistics and clustering-based approaches that better reflect contemporary spatiotemporal climate variability in Central Europe.

Keywords

Quitt climate classification, fixed threshold values, climate variability, normal periods, temperature and precipitation characteristics

Submitted to: Moravian Geographical Reports

1. Introduction

Climate is generally defined as the long-term characteristic weather pattern on Earth or part of it, determined by the variability of the climate system (Czech Meteorological Society, 2025). Therefore, several distinct climate zones can be defined on Earth. People have been trying to understand and describe different climatic conditions since at least the 6th century BC in ancient Greece, but the first evidence-based classification of climate dates back to the turn of the 19th century (Sanderson, 1999).

Climate is often characterised using long-term variability of basic climate variables (such as temperature and precipitation). However, a more comprehensive approach is to classify climate using classifications that simplify the representation of climate conditions, thereby avoiding the need to describe each climate variable (Gupta et al., 2023). However, there is a wide range of approaches for classifying climatic conditions. For instance, the oldest, best-known, and most widely used empirical climate classification, developed by Köppen in 1900, is based on the distribution of temperature and precipitation relative to vegetation (Kottek et al., 2006). Thornthwaite (1948) compiled his classification of climate based on the relationship between potential evapotranspiration and precipitation. However, his system has never been widely spread. On the other hand, Alisov's genetic classification, introduced in 1954, applies large-scale air-mass zones and their seasonal shifts (Alisov, 1954). Papadakis (1967) classified the climate based on the principal crop-ecological characteristics, placing more emphasis on the agricultural potentialities of climates or the climatic requirements of crops. Similar to Alisov's system, Strahler's climate classification defines climates based on large-scale atmospheric circulation and the air masses involved (Strahler, 2013).

As the amount of available data grew during the 20th century, individual classifications were gradually refined and enhanced. Notably, Köppen's classification underwent several modifications. The first adjustment incorporating seasonal temperature and precipitation cycles was made in 1923 (Köppen, 1923), and subsequent modifications followed in the 1930s (Köppen, 1931, 1936). Subsequent significant modifications were made by Geiger (1954, 1961), Trewartha (1968), and Trewartha and Horn (1980).

Various variables were then used for new classifications compilations. For instance, the Global environmental stratification by Metzger (2013) applied a large set of 42 climate variables in a quantitative model that split geographic zones into bioclimate regions. Most recently, Daru (2021) and Calatayud (2021) introduced a new system for classifying climate based on suitable environmental conditions of 26,000 species.

In the face of a rapidly changing climate, the importance of climate classifications is growing. Therefore, it is essential to update climate classifications based on the latest data, ensuring their outputs are as up-to-date as possible and accurately reflect reality. For instance, Peel et al. (2007) produced a high-resolution global update of the Köppen–Geiger classification. Rohli et al. (2015) subsequently introduced an extended framework for the 1981–2010 climate normal period, followed by a European-scale reassessment by Deliège and Nicolay (2016). Most recently, genetic climate classifications such as the Alisov system have also been revisited using data-driven machine learning approaches (Shimabukuro et al., 2023).

Despite the worldwide applicability of Köppen's classification, it is not suitable for the Czech Republic (CR), as more than 80% of its territory falls within the same climate region (Tolasz et al., 2007). Several rather agricultural classification systems were compiled for the territory of the CR, employing various characteristics. For instance, Lang's classification using Lang's rainfall factor, consequential Minář's classification involving moisture certainty, or Kurpelová's classification based on temperature sums and irrigation index (Lang, 1915; Minář, 1948; Kurpelová et al., 1975). A more recent climatic regionalisation of the CR was compiled by Moravec and Votýpka (1998) using data from climatological stations for the period 1961–1990. A more widely known classification is Konček's classification, which was included in the

Climatic Atlas of the Czechoslovak Republic (Vesecký et al., 1958). The best-known and most widely used climate classification in the CR is the Quitt climate classification (Quitt, 1971; Vondráková et al., 2013). However, this classification is based on climate data covering the 1901–1950 period and thus can hardly reflect current climate conditions. Therefore, this study employed the characteristics applied in the Quitt climate classification to describe the climate variability of the CR in the 1961–2020 period. By updating this classification system with the most recent data representing the onset and spread of recent climate change, our study provides answers to the following questions:

1. Is the original Quitt climate classification still relevant to describe the most recent (1991–2020) climate conditions?
2. Can we observe any influence of recent climate change on the functionality of climate classifications represented by the Quitt climate system?
3. If so, are there methods and approaches that would reflect the changing spatiotemporal variability of the recent climate in climate classifications?

The problem was addressed by taking the example of the original Quitt climate classification, which was developed to describe climate conditions in former Czechoslovakia in the first half of the 20th century. An updated version of the original classification system was subsequently applied to the CR, which serves as a representative Central European domain for illustrating the broader methodological challenges posed by static climate classifications in the context of recent climate change.

Section 2 provides a more detailed overview of the climate classifications application. The following Section 3 describes the study area and presents the detailed methodology. The most important findings stemming from the Updated Quitt climate classification are presented in Section 4. Differences between the original and Updated Quitt climate classifications, weaknesses, and comparison with other classification systems are discussed in Section 5. The concluding Section 6 then briefly summarises the main results achieved.

2. Theoretical background

Recent human-induced climate change can be documented by changes in several climate variables (e.g., air temperature, precipitation, cloudiness) (Weart, 2010; Lynas et al., 2021) as well as changes in phenological phases (Menzel et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2024). However, the acceleration of these changes is even faster than most scientists expected (IPCC, 2018). In the case of the mean global temperature increase, it has accelerated by more than 50% since 2010, compared to the 1970–2010 period. The 1970–2010 warming rate of 0.18 °C/decade then almost doubled in the 2010–2023 period (Hansen et al., 2025). Similarly, although the mean decadal temperature rate in the CR between 1961 and 2019 was 0.38 °C, the mean annual temperature in the 2011–2019 period was already about 0.8 °C higher than in the 2001–2010 period (Zahradníček et al., 2021). Climate variables often represent key characteristics across several climate classifications (e.g., the Köppen-Geiger, Metzger, or Quitt systems). The climatic data used in the climate classifications, therefore, have a direct influence on the topicality of a given classification. Thus, this fact should be taken into consideration, and relevant and current climatological data should be used.

Climatic classifications have proven to be a valuable tool in various scientific fields, particularly in climatology, as shown by Cui et al. (2021). Several studies applied classification systems to assess past climate conditions (e.g., Chen and Chen, 2013; Chan and Wu, 2015). However, according to Belda et al. (2014), climatic classifications also serve as a convenient tool for validating climate models (e.g., Lohmann et al., 1993; Kalvová et al., 2003; Belda et al., 2015; Tapiador et al., 2019a,b) as well as for analysing future climate conditions. In view

of the recent climate change, various modifications of the Köppen climate classification were used to project future climate shifts on both global (Rubel and Kotteck, 2010; Belda et al., 2016; Beck et al., 2018; Valjarević et al., 2022) and regional scales (Gerstengarbe and Werner, 2009; Feng et al., 2012; Gallardo et al., 2013; Fernandez et al., 2017; Rubel et al., 2017; Bindhu et al., 2021). Similarly, Skalák et al. (2018) employed high-resolution, bias-corrected simulations of two regional models to project shifts in Köppen–Geiger zones in Central Europe by the end of the 21st century, depicting the influence of changing climate zones on ecosystems and society. Some shifts in Köppen climatic regions towards higher altitudes and to the north were registered in Slovakia during the 20th and early 21st centuries (Melo et al., 2013). Similarly, a large-scale shift in agroclimatic zones, evaluated based on climatological and rain-gauge stations in the CR between 1961 and 2019, was revealed by Trnka et al. (2021). Except for climatology, climate classifications are also applied in bioclimatology (Wang and Overland, 2004; Błażejczyk et al., 2015), ecosystem geography (Bailey, 2009; Baker et al., 2010), agriculture (Whelen and Siqueira, 2018; Hadria et al., 2019; Orrego-Verdugo et al., 2021), hydrology (Tang and Hossain, 2012; Pimental-Rodrigues and Silva-Afonso, 2023; Amihăesei et al., 2024), or to assess classifications' application in the building energy efficiency sector (Gupta et al., 2023).

Although the Quitt climate classification (Fig. 1) is the most widely used classification system in the CR, only a several studies have addressed its update. The first known update was carried out by Tolasz et al. (2007) in the Atlas of Czechia. Along with subsequent works by Hrnčiarová et al. (2009) and Vondráková et al. (2013), which have all applied the original 14 climatic characteristics defined by Quitt (1971) to the 1961–2000 period. To determine whether a widely used Quitt climate classification remains a viable tool in the context of recent climate change, it is essential to test its relevance using the most recent internationally recognised 1991–2020 period, ensuring comparability with contemporary international research.

Therefore, the aims of this study are:

- update the original Quitt climate classification using the most recent climate data,
- analyse the pronounced climate variability of the Czech Republic in the 1961–2020 period based on original climatic characteristics defined by Quitt (1971),
- evaluate the applicability of the original static-threshold Quitt climate classification, and
- present methods and approaches that can be applied to evaluate changing climate conditions via climate classifications in a long-term view across various countries over the last 60 years.

Fig. 1: Original Quitt climate classification representing the 1901–1950 period.
Source: Quitt 1971, modified by authors

3. Materials and methods

3.1. The study area

The study area (the CR) lies within Central Europe and belongs to the temperate climate zone. This geographic position results in a convergence of oceanic and continental climatic influences, with continental effects increasing toward the southeast of the country. Consequently, the CR exhibits pronounced spatial climatic variability, despite its relatively small area (78,871 km²) and modest altitudinal range, spanning from the lowest point (115 m a.s.l.) to the highest (1,603 m a.s.l.; Fig. 2a; CSO, 2024).

In the 1961–2020 period, mean annual air temperatures in CR ranged from 0.9 °C to 10.0 °C (with 67% of the area between 7.0 °C and 9.0 °C), showing a clear correspondence with altitude (Fig. 2b). Annual precipitation totals across most of the country ranged from 600 to 700 mm (38 % of the area), with extremes from 458 mm in rain-shadow areas (Žatec region, northwestern CR) up to 1,400 mm in the wettest mountain regions of the Krkonoše Mountains (north CR, Fig. 2c). Snow cover duration most frequently ranged between 40 and 60 days per year (38 % of the area), with extremes from 21 days in the lowest elevations to 188 days in the highest mountain areas, where snow cover persisted from November to April.

Long-term trends in the main climate variables for the period 1961–2020 varied in both intensity and spatial distribution. While the statistically significant increase in mean annual air temperature is widespread across the whole country (Fig. 3a), annual precipitation totals exhibited regional differences, with a tendency to increase in the western and southwestern parts of the CR (statistically significant only in marginal area) and to decrease in the eastern regions (Fig. 3b). A statistically significant decreasing trend in snow cover duration was observed across most of the country, with the most substantial decrease occurring at higher elevations (Fig. 3c).

Fig. 2: Hypsometric map of the Czech Republic (a), mean annual temperatures (°C) (b), and mean annual precipitation totals (mm) (c) in the 1961–2020 period. Source: authors' calculations

3.2. Data quality control and data homogenisation

All analyses were based on in situ measurements from the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI, 2026). The dataset covered the 1961–2020 period and included daily mean, maximum, and minimum air temperature from 268 stations, daily sums of global radiation from 305 stations, and daily precipitation totals from 787 stations. Prior to homogenisation, the data underwent standard quality control following Štěpánek et al. (2011).

Data homogenisation was performed following the methodology of Štěpánek et al. (2013) for all meteorological variables, except snow cover duration, which was homogenised for the first time in the CR in this study based on raw CHMI data. In case of snow cover, the input dataset consisted of records from 595 stations with at least 40 years of available data for the snow year during the 1961–2020 period. The snow year was defined from 1 July of the previous year to 30 June of the following year, ensuring that individual snow years were not split across calendar years. Stations were divided into two groups: complete and incomplete (containing one or more incomplete seasons). For each station, the Pearson correlation coefficient (R) was calculated with every complete station. Then, a reference series was created for each station (both complete and incomplete) by combining the three complete stations with the highest R values. Additional complete stations were included in the reference series if they met two criteria: $R > 0.85$ and R exceeding the 95th percentile of all computed coefficients.

Subsequently, initial quality control of snow cover was performed for each station based on its reference series, and statistically significant breakpoints were identified using the standard normal homogeneity test (SNHT; Alexandersson, 1986), which has previously been applied for similar purposes in the Alpine region (Marcolini et al., 2017). Values of snow cover days prior to a detected breakpoint were adjusted using a correction factor calculated from the ratio of medians before and after the breakpoint. Since the SNHT detected only a single breakpoint, a second iteration of homogenisation was conducted under the same conditions as the first iteration, using the time series obtained from the first iteration as input. Overall, at least one breakpoint was detected in 49% of stations (37% in the first iteration), and two breakpoints in 7% of stations. After homogenisation, missing values were filled in using a Random Forest machine learning model, which demonstrated a lower mean root mean square error (RMSE) compared to a linear regression model.

After homogenisation, mean annual values were calculated for each station for the 1961–2020 period (radiation characteristics were derived using the methodology of Tolasz et al. (2007)), serving as input for spatial interpolation. Spatial interpolation was conducted using regression kriging (for radiation variables, the inverse distance weighting method was applied) in ProClimDB software (Štěpánek, 2009) at a spatial resolution of 500×500 m. The model accounted for statistically significant relationships between meteorological variables and geographic factors, such as elevation, latitude, longitude, surface roughness, slope, and aspect. Finally, decadal linear trends were analysed using the Theil–Sen estimator (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1992), and their statistical significance was assessed with the Mann–Kendall test at a 0.05 significance level (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1975). Topographical layers used in Fig. 2–4 were used from ArcData, 2016.

Fig. 3: 10-year trends of mean annual temperature (°C) (a), mean annual precipitation totals (mm) (b), and mean annual number of days with snow cover in the winter season (c) in the Czech Republic in the 1961–2020 period. Temperature trends are statistically significant across the Czech Republic. Source: authors' calculations

3.3. Revision of the Quitt climate classification

The Updated Quitt classification was created in accordance with the original methodology established by Quitt (1971). For each climate normal period, the same 14 input climatic characteristics were derived from the gridded datasets homogenised instrumental series and averaged over both normal periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020). For each grid cell, the values of individual climatic characteristics were compared with their predefined threshold values (Appendix 1) for the 23 climatic regions established by Quitt (1971). The final climatic region for each grid cell was determined as the region with the highest number of climatic characteristics that met their threshold values. When the maximum number of thresholds was met across multiple climatic regions, a hierarchical decision system was applied. At the first level (resolving most ambiguities), the climatic region with the highest sum of weights of all climatic characteristics falling within the threshold range was selected, with weights assigned to each characteristic according to the original methodology (Quitt 1971). If ambiguity persisted, subsequent hierarchical levels were applied in order of significance according to the original methodology: mean July air temperatures (2nd level), mean January air temperatures (3rd level), April–September (summer half-year) precipitation totals (4th level), and snow cover duration (5th level), which resolved all remaining ambiguities. The original division into three main groups of climatic regions (Warm, Moderately Warm, and Cold) with their names (W1–W5, MW1–MW11, and C1–C7) was also preserved. This methodological approach enables direct comparison between the Original and the Updated classification version.

4. Results

4.1 Updated Quitt climate classification

The Updated Quitt climate classification distinguishes a total of 23 climatic regions, grouped into three main groups: Warm (5 regions, W1–W5), Moderately Warm (11 regions, MW1–MW11), and Cold (7 regions, C1–C7). During the 1961–1990 period (Fig. 4a), the Warm group covered contiguous areas at low elevations, particularly in the basins of the Dyje, Morava, Odra, Labe, and lower Vltava rivers. The Moderately Warm group was present in mid-altitude regions, such as the Bohemian-Moravian Highlands and northern Bohemia. The Cold group was located in mountainous and foothill areas, including all major mountain ranges; however, it also included some slightly lower-elevated areas, such as parts of the Bohemian-Moravian Highlands and the Nízký Jeseník Mountains, reaching as low as 600 m a.s.l.

During the 1991–2020 period (Fig. 4b), a pronounced spatial shift was observed compared to the 1961–1990 period. The Warm group exhibited the most significant expansion, extending into lower elevations of southern and western Bohemia as well as the Frýdlant Promontory (northern Bohemia), in some cases reaching as high as 500 m a.s.l. The warmest climatic region, W5, expanded across extensive lowland regions of the CR. The Moderately Warm group covered, for example, the entire Bohemian-Moravian Highlands and the Nízký Jeseník Mountains, while the Cold group remained confined only to the highest mountain ranges of the country, mainly above 800 m a.s.l.

Fig. 4: Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic with 23 climatic regions divided into three groups of climatic regions for a) 1961–1990 and b) 1991–2020 periods. Source: authors' elaboration

4.2 Shifts in climatic regions

Changes in the spatial extent of climatic regions between the periods 1961–1990 and 1991–2020, presented in Fig. 5, confirm a substantial expansion of the Warm group, which increased by 29.7% of the CR's territory. Simultaneously, the area of the Moderately Warm group decreased by 21.2%, and the Cold group by 8.5% of the national territory. The expansion of

regions W2 and W5 primarily drove the increase in the Warm group. In contrast, region W5 became the most widespread in the 1991–2020 period, covering 25.9% of the CR and newly including nine regional capitals that were not part of this region in the 1961–1990 period (e.g., Plzeň and Zlín). Changes between W2 and W5 accounted for 15% of all observed shifts between both periods, representing the largest single change across the regions.

Fig 5: Sankey diagram of the shift of climatic regions of the Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic between both periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020). Groups of climatic regions: W – Warm, MW – Moderately warm, C – Cold. The percentages of the most widespread climatic regions and their individual shifts are given in parentheses. Source: authors' elaboration

The main reason for the reduction in the Moderately Warm group area was the reassignment of areas previously within MW11 to individual regions of the Warm group, particularly to W2 in southern and western Bohemia, which represented the second-largest area transfer between the periods. Another contributing factor was region MW7, the most extensive region in the 1961–1990 period, covering 17% of the territory, also located mainly in southern and western Bohemia. Half of MW7's area was incorporated into W2, while the remaining half was reassigned to MW10, which became the main region of the Moderately Warm group in the 1991–2020 period, covering 12% of the CR. The Cold group covered only 5% of the CR in the 1991–2020 period, documenting a pronounced retreat of Cold regions from most of the territory, with persistence only at the highest elevations. The most widespread climatic region within the Cold group remained C7, as in the 1961–1990 period. In the 1991–2020 period, C7

incorporated parts of relatively cooler regions, such as C4, while its marginal areas were reassigned to warmer regions, MW4 and MW7 (Fig. 5).

4.3 Climatic variability and elevation differences

The elevational gradient was maintained across both study periods, ranging from the lowest Warm region W5 to the highest peaks of the CR within C1. In the 1991–2020 period, this gradient was more pronounced, particularly within the Cold group, resulting in the disappearance of some classes (e.g. C2 and C4). The boundary between the Moderately Warm and Cold groups rose from 650 m a.s.l. (1961–1990) to 800 m a.s.l. (1991–2020). Similarly, the boundary between the Warm and Moderately Warm groups shifted upward from 400 m a.s.l. to 500 m a.s.l. A comparison of the studied periods revealed an overall upward shift, averaging 133 m a.s.l. across regions with a detected upward shift. The most pronounced median elevation increases were observed in MW2 and MW4, rising by 220 m, whereas two regions experienced decreases: MW8 (10 m) and MW6 (60 m). The warmest region, W5, extended up to 300 m a.s.l. in the 1991–2020 period (compared to 200 m a.s.l. in the 1961–1990 period), whereas the coldest region, C1, was located entirely above 1,300 m a.s.l. (compared to 1,100 m a.s.l. in the 1961–1990 period) (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Elevation (m a.s.l.) for 23 climatic regions of the Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic, divided into three groups of climatic regions: 1 – Warm, 2 – Moderately Warm and 3 – Cold, for both studied periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020). Source: authors' elaboration

The observed shifts in the distributions of temperature and precipitation characteristics between both periods indicate that the threshold ranges originally defined by Quitt for individual climatic regions no longer correspond to the climatic conditions of the CR during the 1991–2020 period. For instance, in the case of the mean temperature, both the mean and median values ($-1.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) shifted into the warmest region, W5. As regards the thresholds for mean January temperature, 75% of the CR territory fell within the warmest (W5) region in the 1991–2020 period, while only the remaining 25% of the territory was distributed across the remaining 22 climatic

regions. No grid cells in the coldest regions (C1–C3) fitted within their predefined temperature range (Fig. 7a), even though they were classified into the coldest regions based on other characteristics using the algorithm described in Methods (Section 3.3).

The decrease in the mean annual number of days with snow cover (from 65 to 53 days on average in the CR) led to its uneven distribution among climatic regions. In the 1991–2020 period, the share of grid cells that fitted into the T5 range for this characteristic increased from 11.2% to 26.5%. Collectively, 39.1% of the CR area fell within the ranges of regions W5, W4, and W2 on days with snow cover. In the 1991–2020 period, no grid cells in climatic regions C1 and C2 met the snow cover duration threshold (Fig. 7b).

5. Discussion

Assessing the relevance of the Updated Quitt climate classification in the context of recent climate change requires verifying the methodological robustness of the original Quitt (1971) methodology. A comparison between the original Quitt's climate classification (representing the 1901–1950 period) and its Updated version for the 1961–1990 period revealed only minor differences in the spatial delineation of individual climatic regions. In the original version, the Warm, Moderately Warm, and Cold regions covered 19.5%, 66.9%, and 13.6% of the CR, respectively. In the updated version for the 1961–1990 period, these proportions were 27.0%, 59.5%, and 13.5%, respectively. The only notable change was the expansion of the Warm region into the Ostrava Basin in north-eastern CR at the expense of the Moderately Warm region. The detected discrepancies can be attributed to the initial effects of climate change already occurring during the 1961–1990 period, as well as to minor methodological differences stemming from the lack of available detailed methodology of the original punch-card-based procedure. Overall, the updated version faithfully reproduces the fundamental structure of Quitt's classification system.

Both temperature and precipitation characteristics during the 1991–2020 period frequently exceeded the original minimum and maximum threshold values defined by Quitt for individual climatic regions. This discrepancy was not limited to temperature characteristics – for instance, up to 48% of the CR's territory recorded October–March precipitation totals below the lowest predefined threshold of 350 mm. In such cases, lower threshold values would be more appropriate, whereas for temperature characteristics, higher thresholds than those originally defined by Quitt would be required. The data distribution clearly confirms that climatic conditions in the 1991–2020 period have shifted beyond the range that Quitt defined as representative for individual climatic regions based on observations from the 1901–1950 period. Moreover, the data were not evenly distributed across all 23 climatic regions but often clustered within a single threshold interval, thereby reducing the explanatory value of the climatic regionalisation of the CR (Section 4.3). This may also lead to abrupt shifts in the resulting classification if the method is applied in the future.

Fig. 7: Histograms of two selected input characteristics of the Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic for both studied periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020), including threshold values of 23 climatic regions according to Quitt (1971): mean daily air temperature in January (°C) (a) and mean number of days with snow cover (b). Source: authors' elaboration

The inadequacy of the originally defined threshold values resulted in low internal consistency within the delineated climatic regions during the 1991–2020 period. On average, across all climatic regions, 11 of the 14 evaluated climatic characteristics matched their prescribed thresholds in the 1961–1990 period, whereas only eight characteristics corresponded in the 1991–2020 period. According to the original methodology, a climatic region was required to satisfy at least 12 of the 14 principal characteristics (Quitt, 1971). This condition was fulfilled in only 4.7% of the CR's territory in the 1991–2020 period (compared to 67.4% in the 1961–

1990 period), clearly demonstrating a loss of diagnostic robustness in the original classification method.

For a more detailed comparison between observed values from both periods and the original threshold limits, the most extensive regions of each climatic group were examined: C7 (Cold), MW10 (Moderately Warm), and W5 (Warm). On average, 65% of data in the 1961–1990 period and 69% in the 1991–2020 period met their respective thresholds, with agreement above 80% being rather exceptional. This effect primarily resulted from the high-temperature thresholds in the C7 and W5 regions already during the 1961–1990 period. Moreover, while most characteristics remained below the defined thresholds in the 1961–1990 period, they frequently exceeded them in the 1991–2020 period (Appendix 2). The most pronounced discrepancies between both periods were observed in the warmest region, W5, where temperature characteristics remained highly consistent, whereas April–September precipitation totals met the prescribed thresholds in only 40% of cases (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Distribution of two selected input characteristics of the Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic: mean July air temperature (°C) (a) and April–September precipitation total (mm) (b) for the climatic region W5 in both normal periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020, the percentage of values corresponds to the thresholds of climatic region W5 according to Quitt (1971), the dependence of mean July air temperature (°C) (c) and April–September precipitation total (mm) (d) on altitude (R^2 represents the coefficient of determination of this dependence). Source: authors' elaboration

Quitt's classification system was predominantly based on temperature characteristics: of the original 14 climatic indicators, eight were temperature-related, and only four were precipitation-related. This structural imbalance, combined with the substantial warming observed in the 1991–2020 period, resulted in an upward shift of the climatic regions by an average of 133 m a.s.l., corresponding to the elevation at which similar temperatures occurred in lower altitudes during the 1961–1990 period. However, this vertical shift also relocated the climatic regions into areas with higher precipitation totals, thereby disrupting the pairing between temperature and precipitation characteristics that Quitt's original method relied on. Specifically, the warmest climatic region, W5, shifted on average from 150–200 m a.s.l. in the 1961–1990 period up to approximately 250–300 m a.s.l. in the 1991–2020 period. While

median April–September precipitation totals in this region were 316 mm in the 1961–1990 period, they increased to 378 mm in the 1991–2020 period (Fig. 8), which is inconsistent with Quitt’s original limit. In general, corresponding mean temperatures were paired with higher precipitation totals in the 1991–2020 period than in the 1961–1990 or 1901–1950 periods used in the original method. Consequently, climatic regions defined by the methodology developed for the 1901–1950 baseline no longer simultaneously met both temperature and precipitation criteria, which constitutes the principal reason Quitt’s classification fails to represent contemporary climatic conditions.

The results of this study underscore the need to abandon classification methods based on fixed thresholds – not only in the CR but also in a broader international context. Many widely used climatic classification systems (e.g., Köppen, 1900; Thornthwaite, 1948; Geiger, 1961; Trewartha, 1968; Kottke et al., 2006) still rely on fixed thresholds; however, as noted by Cui, Liang, and Wang (2021), their explanatory power progressively declines under recent climate change, highlighting the need for methodological revision. While fixed thresholds have proven useful for illustrating the impacts of climate change (e.g., Trnka et al., 2011; Skalák et al., 2018; Torbenson et al., 2024), their original purpose, i.e. to meaningfully delineate climatic regions according to characteristic climate conditions, has increasingly been compromised. To more accurately capture the spatiotemporal variability of climate, multidimensional statistical analyses and modern clustering techniques are preferable (e.g., Tapiador et al., 2019a), as applied by Crespi et al. (2023) in neighbouring Germany. These approaches allow climatic regions to be delineated according to the actual distribution of climatic characteristics, rendering the resulting classification methodologically robust and relevant under current and future climate change.

It is also important to emphasise that boundaries between climatic regions are more complex than suggested by static, fixed thresholds, and that modern clustering methods can better reflect this complexity. Building on this, more robust, continental-scale classifications provide an additional perspective. For example, the environmental stratification of Europe proposed by Metzger et al. (2005) offers a more robust framework for climatic regionalisation at larger spatial scales. Nevertheless, even in these approaches, inconsistencies in the temperature–precipitation relationship have been reported (Metzger et al., 2008), although this does not preclude their practical application. To increase the reliability of future classifications, additional climate-related variables, particularly soil moisture and soil temperature, could be incorporated, potentially providing a more realistic representation of land–atmosphere interactions than the traditional temperature–precipitation framework alone (e.g., Trnka et al., 2013).

6. Conclusions and suggestions for relevant research and practice

Is the Quitt climate classification still relevant? The results of this study unequivocally demonstrate that, despite the high fidelity of the Updated Quitt climate classification across both normal periods, its validity can no longer be considered robust or representative for the 1991–2020 period. The key conclusions are as follows:

- (i) The fixed and static thresholds established by Quitt (1971) no longer correspond to the distribution of observed climatic indicators during the 1991–2020 period and are insufficiently representative of contemporary climate conditions in Central Europe.
- (ii) The failure of the Quitt classification system during the 1991–2020 period is directly caused by recent climate change and its effect on the variability of basic climate variables. Their systematic exceedance of the defined thresholds leads to an uneven partitioning of the input characteristics. On average, six of the fourteen characteristics did not meet the predefined limits across the climatic regions, rendering the classification's sensitivity obsolete.

- (iii) The principal reason for the aforementioned failure is the disruption of internal consistency (pairing) between temperature and precipitation characteristics – rising air temperatures during the 1991–2020 period shifted climatic regions to higher, naturally more precipitation-rich elevations, while precipitation totals did not significantly change.
- (iv) Therefore, we recommend replacing traditional classification schemes with approaches based on multivariate statistics and modern clustering analyses. Such methods should more accurately capture the spatiotemporal variability of climate and remain methodologically robust under recent climate change.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge support from AdAgriF - Advanced methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest landscape for climate change mitigation (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635) and from Czech Science Foundation, project No. 24–14581 L, Atmospheric circulation and weather extremes in Central Europe and their representation in climate models (GAČR 24–14581 L). PZ was supported by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, project No. MZE/QL QL24020351.

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Appendix 2: Percentage of values corresponding to the Quitt (1971) thresholds for selected input characteristics of the Updated Quitt climate classification of the Czech Republic: mean daily air temperature in July (Tmean July – °C) (a), mean daily air temperature in January (Tmean January – °C) (b), April–September precipitation totals (Prec SHY – mm) (c) and mean number of days with snow cover (SCD – d) in both normal periods (1961–1990 and 1991–2020) for three selected climatic regions representing the largest areas of each climatic region: C7, MW10, and W5. Source: author’s calculations

Climatic region	Climate characteristic	Threshold value		Threshold range (%)			
		min	max	1NP	others	2NP	others
C7	Tmean July	15	16	58.7	lower	77.5	lower
	Tmean January	-4	-3	51.3	lower	75.8	higher
	TP SHY	500	600	34.1	lower	61.4	lower
	SCD	100	120	28.4	lower	53.1	lower
MW10	Tmean July	16	17	97.9	lower	33.6	higher
	Tmean January	-3	-2	68.4	lower	86.4	higher
	TP SHY	400	450	56.9	lower	44.9	higher
	SCD	60	80	84.5	lower	90.4	higher
W5	Tmean July	19	NA	0.2	lower	96.5	lower
	Tmean January	-2	NA	86.1	lower	100.0	-
	TP SHY	NA	350	95.1	higher	40.0	higher
	SCD	NA	40	96.4	higher	95.6	higher